

High Power Supply Rejection LDO Regulator for Switching Applications

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Abstract—The paper describes design and analysis of a Low-Dropout Regulator (LDO) with a high value of the power supply rejection (PSR) at high frequencies (above 10MHz). The proposed LDO was designed in a standard 65 nm CMOS technology. The output of the designed LDO can be adjusted by the voltage reference used in the LDO. The obtained results prove a very good PSR parameter at frequencies above 10 MHz, where the value of -40 dB is observed in the worst case. Additionally, the designed LDO topology exhibits promising load regulation properties even for a low value of the output capacitor. The proposed LDO can be fully integrated on a chip, and used in complex switching converter Systems on-Chip (SoC), where a high value of PSR is required.

I. INTRODUCTION

Recent advanced electronic systems contain different cores (e.g. analog, digital, RF, etc.), which can be implemented on a single chip, and known as System-on-Chip (SoC). In order to distribute the power supply for all parts of a SoC, different voltage domains need to be implemented. Therefore, sensitive analog building blocks have to be shielded from undesired fluctuations on the supply rails and switching noise generated by digital parts of a mixed-signal system. Thus, analog building blocks require a high value of the PSR parameter so that they could work correctly also under such noisy operation conditions. A regulated supply voltage source can suppress variations and switching noise present on the supply rails of analog blocks, and also improve the overall performances. For this reason, a regulated power supply source is one of the most important block used in complex SoCs, and its design still brings challenges for designers of integrated circuits (IC).

The voltage regulation can be based on an LDO regulator or a switch-mode converter. In complex SoCs, where energy harvesters are used as the input voltage source, the switch-mode DC-DC converters represent better choice because of their high power-conversion performance. However, the output of a switch-mode voltage converter needs to be filtered for elimination of the switching noise. LDO regulator can suppress noise and fluctuations at the output of a DC-DC converter. In such a case, high PSR performance of the LDO is required. First of all, the LDO has to remove noise generated at switching frequency of the DC-DC converter. In the case of a fully on-chip DC-DC converter, its switching frequency is usually in the range of tens or hundreds of

MHz. Therefore, the value of PSR at high frequencies (above 10 MHz) is the most important requirement determining the LDO topology selection.

For the reasons described above, it is important to focus on development of LDO topologies that are able to suppress the high-frequency switching noise. In this paper, we focused on the design and verification of a fully on-chip LDO with a high value of the PSR parameter at high frequencies. Thus, such a LDO topology could be used in complex switching applications fully integrated on a chip. Section II contains a short overview of techniques to obtain the high PSR. The designed LDO and its main circuit blocks are described in Section III. Achieved results obtained by simulation of the proposed LDO circuit are presented in Section IV. A discussion of the results is provided in Section V, while conclusions are drawn in Section VI.

II. BACKGROUND

In order to improve PSR performance of the LDO, different techniques were introduced [1]–[8]. One of the most common solutions is to introduce a low-pass filter in the supply line [1]. However, this solution reduces a voltage headroom due to a serial resistor. Another solution, described in [1], uses two LDO regulators connected in series, but in the case of on-chip realization, a considerable chip area overhead might be unacceptable. In [7], a cascode NMOS transistor with an NMOS pass device was employed to isolate noise on the supply rail. However, a need of two charge pumps controlling the NMOS transistors increases complexity of such a topology. The high PSR performance in a wide frequency range can be achieved using an NMOS device to cascode the PMOS pass device that is described in [1], [6]. On the other hand, it is important to ensure appropriate operation conditions of the cascode NMOS over the process, temperature a voltage (PVT) variations. In the case of a fully on-chip implementation, a value of the output capacitor is also limited. Last but not least requirement is the power consumption of the whole LDO. Since the battery life of portable electronics needs to be increased, the power consumption of all complex SoC should be decreased as much as possible. Feed-forward supply-noise cancellation technique, used in [3], reaches very good PSR performance but for cost of a rather high power consumption. Therefore, it is not easy to find the best solution that should

take into account all these aspects during the design of a low-power LDO with the high PSR performance.

III. PROPOSED LDO TOPOLOGY

The designed LDO is based on the concept described in [9]–[11], which focuses on the slew-rate improvement by introducing transient recovery time enhancement block [10]. In order to improve the PSR performance at high frequencies, in this work, an NMOS transistor connected in a cascode with the PMOS pass device was used. In such a way, the proposed LDO offers very good slew-rate and PSR performance with relatively small value of the output capacitor (from 100 pF to 200 pF). The LDO output voltage was set to 1.2 V, and the input voltage range is from 1.5 V to 2 V. Since a charge pump used in LDO multiplies the input voltage by 2, the upper limit of the input voltage range is 2 V. Since the LDO will be aimed for the ultra-low-power systems, the output current range from 1 μA to 300 μA and the dropout voltage of 0.3 V (in the worst case) were the main design requirements.

General block diagram of the proposed LDO is shown in Fig. 1. The PMOS pass device is driven by an error amplifier (EA) based on the differential source-cross-coupled topology presented in more detail in [10]. In comparison to the topology presented in [10], a slew-rate (SR) enhancement block was used in our research. The output current of this circuit depends on the LDO output current (Fig. 2). The output current flowing through the PMOS pass device is mirrored to MP_2 and then, via non-inverting stage (MP_3 and MP_4) to the transistor MN_3 . MN_3 and MN_2 devices form another current mirror with the mirroring ratio of 1:10. In this way, MN_2 can sink 10% of the output load current and improve transition response of the proposed LDO.

Since the main application area of the proposed LDO includes on-chip switching converters, the PSR performance represents one of the most important parameters. In our case, NMOS transistor was used to cascode the pass device, and improve the PSR performance at frequencies above 10 MHz. From the analysis presented in [12], one can observe that the NMOS device can help improve the overall PSR of LDO if its output resistance is increased. However, the main challenge of this approach is to ensure that NMOS device will be working in the saturation region even under the dropout conditions. Additionally, the saturation region needs to be kept in all process corners. Therefore, in the proposed LDO architecture, so-called V_{DS} "keeper" circuit was used to provide a stable drain-source voltage over the process and temperature variations. The "keeper" consists of a difference amplifier containing resistors R_{D1} – R_{D4} introduced in Fig. 1. If we consider that $R_{D1} = R_{D2} = R_{D3} = R_{D4}$, V_{DS} of the NMOS pass device will be equal to V_{REF} voltage. In our case, the voltage reference has the output voltage of about 0.2 V which means that the V_{DS} value of the NMOS cascode device will be kept to 0.2 V. Finally, from the high PSR performance point of view, the voltage reference and the error amplifier with a slew-rate enhancement circuit are powered from the local

supply voltage V_{LOCAL} (source of NMOS cascode device) which helps reaching very good PSR at high frequencies.

The last block of the proposed LDO regulator is the voltage reference. As mentioned above, the output voltage value of the reference circuit is 0.2 V. In order to set an appropriate value of the reference voltage for the LDO, a tunable buffer is employed, and the output voltage V_{REF_BUF} of 1.2 V was adjusted.

IV. ACHIEVED RESULTS

The results obtained by simulation of the proposed LDO are presented in this section. Fabrication process fluctuations were taken into account, and LDO was simulated using Corner Analysis. The temperature range from -20°C to 85°C was considered in all simulations.

Transfer characteristics (dependence of the output voltage on the input voltage) represent the most important feature of the LDO. In Fig. 3, the transfer characteristics of the proposed LDO for the output load current of 100 μA obtained over the process corners is shown. The deviation of 13 mV in the output voltage over the process corners and temperature can be observed. The output voltage value deviates from 1.192 V to 1.205 V that is mainly caused by the voltage reference inaccuracy. The minimum input voltage in the worst case is 1.44 V.

The parameter which is directly related to the transfer characteristics is the dropout voltage of LDO depicted in Fig. 4. The dropout voltage was obtained for different output currents in whole temperature range over the corners. In the worst case, the dropout voltage of 270 mV was observed for the output current of 300 μA . In the best case, for the maximum output current, the dropout voltage will be below 0.2 V. From Fig. 4, it can be observed that for the output current up to 100 μA , the dropout voltage is relatively constant while for higher current, the dropout value increases exponentially.

The dependence of LDO output voltage on temperature is another important parameter. This dependence for input range from 1.45 V to 2 V and output current of 100 μA over the process corners are shown in Fig. 5. In the best case, temperature coefficient (TC) of the output voltage of 14 ppm/ $^\circ\text{C}$ is achieved. On the other hand, the worst case represents FNSP corner where the TC is 194 ppm/ $^\circ\text{C}$. It is important to note, that shape of temperature dependence is mainly given by internal voltage reference used in LDO. The presented results are for trimmed temperature coefficient of voltage reference which is implemented in the LDO using the digital trimming technique but it is not subject of this article. Here, we can conclude that obtained accuracy of LDO will be sufficient for target application in switching converter.

In order to investigate the dynamic behavior and performance of the proposed LDO, the input voltage step from 1.5 V to 1.6 V and output current step from 1 μA to 100 μA were applied. The dynamic response to the input voltage step is shown in Fig. 6, for the output current value of 100 μA . It can be observed that the proposed LDO has good response to

Fig. 1. General block diagram of the proposed LDO

the input voltage step where overshoot and undershoot in less than 10 mV occurred.

The dynamic response of LDO on the output current step is depicted in Fig. 7. This simulation was done for the input voltage value of 1.6 V. One can observe that LDO response provides good stability, and the recovery time is in the range of tens μ s. The presented results were obtained with the slew-rate enhancement circuit. However, with the SR enhancement circuit, the overall power consumption will be increased.

For better analysis of the dynamic performance, we also investigated line and load regulation parameters (LNR and LDR). Dependence of LDR parameter as a function of the input voltage obtained for all process corners and temperature range from -20°C to 85°C is shown in Fig. 8. The worst case value of LDR parameter (2.29 %/mA) can be observed for the minimum input voltage of 1.45 V, while the best LDR value of 0.002 %/mA was achieved for the maximum input voltage.

The dependence of LNR parameter on the output current is shown in Fig. 9, where we investigated LNR deviations caused

Fig. 3. Transfer characteristics of LDO over process corners ($I_{OUT} = 100\mu\text{A}$; $T = -20^\circ\text{C} \div 85^\circ\text{C}$)

Fig. 2. Schematic diagram of the SR enhancement part of LDO

Fig. 4. Dropout voltage over process corners ($V_{IN} = V_{INmin}$; $T = -20^\circ\text{C} \div 85^\circ\text{C}$)

by process and temperature fluctuations. It can be observed that the deviation of line regulation is constant over the whole range of output current. The only difference can be observed

Fig. 5. The output voltage over temperature and process corners ($V_{IN} = 1.45V \div 2V$; $I_{OUT} = 0.1mA$)

Fig. 6. LDO response to the input voltage change

Fig. 7. LDO response to output current change

for $1 \mu A$, where LNR parameter reaches value of 0.06 %. Such excellent result was achieved using a NMOS cascode device, as well as the high value of loop gain introduced by the error amplifier.

For the purpose of stability, we investigate gain margin (GM) and phase margin (PM) of the EA feedback loop. From the stability point of view, the worst case represents the low output current and the low input voltage. Therefore, we

Fig. 8. LDR parameter of the proposed LDO ($I_{OUT} = 1\mu A \div 300\mu A$)

Fig. 9. LNR parameter of the proposed LDO ($V_{IN} = 0.45V \div 1.2V$)

consider output current of $10 \mu A$ and supply voltage of $1.5 V$. The results of GM and PM obtained from stability analysis of LDO are shown Fig. 10. In the worst case, PM of 51.46° was achieved in the SNSP corner (slow corner). The worst case for GM is reported in the FNFP corner (fast corner), where the value of 22.46 dB was reached. The best corner from the

Fig. 10. Gain and phase margin of the EA feedback loop ($V_{IN} = 1.5V$; $I_{OUT} = 10\mu A$)

stability point of view, is the FNFP for PM and SNSP for GM, respectively. Gain bandwidth (GBW) of the EA feedback loop varies from 32 kHz to 1.52 MHz depending on the output current value and process corner. We also verified stability for marginal values of the output current, where in the worst case corner, PM is 24.8° and $>60^\circ$ for the current value of $1 \mu A$ and $300 \mu A$, respectively. Despite such a low value of PM, we can consider that the proposed LDO will be stable but the settling time might be unacceptably large. Since the designed LDO will be used to supply a sensitive analog circuit, the output current should be larger than $1 \mu A$. Finally, it is important to note that stability of the EA feedback loop used to keep the NMOS pass device in saturation region (Fig. 1) was also investigated. Here, values higher than 54° and 60 dB (in all process corners and the whole range of output current) for PM and GM was achieved, respectively. The GBW of the feedback loop varies from 8.5 kHz to 19.5 kHz.

In order to show the improvement obtained using a PMOS pass device cascoded by a NMOS transistor, we compared the PSR performance with and without the cascode transistor. The result of comparison is depicted in Fig. 11, where one can observe that the PSR performance will be improved by 20 dB at frequency values above 10 MHz. Additionally, the minimum PSR will be shifted to the higher frequencies, and it will be improved by 3 dB. The PSR at lower frequencies will be the same as without the NMOS cascode device. From Fig. 11 we can conclude that the cascode NMOS represents a simple low-power solution for improving PSR feature of the LDO regulator.

Fig. 11. Comparison of PSR performance ($V_{IN} = 1.5V$; $I_{OUT} = 100\mu A$)

The PSR results obtained by simulation are shown in Fig. 12. As can be observed, the PSRR at low frequency reaches value of -68.5 dB, while at frequency of 10 MHz, the PSR of -41.6 dB was achieved. In the whole frequency range, the worst value of PSR is -21.4 dB. The presented PSR performance was obtained with the load capacitor value of 150 pF. The results can be further improved by increasing the value of output load capacitor.

The main achieved parameters of the proposed LDO are summarized in Table I, where all process corners and the temperature range from $-20^\circ C$ to $85^\circ C$ are considered. It is

Fig. 12. PSR of the proposed LDO ($V_{IN} = 1.5V$; $I_{OUT} = 100\mu A$)

important to note that the power consumption is increased if the slew-rate enhancement circuit, since the sinking current is 10 %. However, the PSR performance of the proposed LDO does not depend on the slew-rate enhancement circuit, and a value lower than -40 dB for output current $100 \mu A$ at frequency of 10 MHz was achieved. For higher output currents, the PSR will be worse (the value of -28.7 dB can be observed for the maximum output current).

TABLE I
MAIN PARAMETERS OF THE PROPOSED LDO

Parameter	Min	Typ	Max	Unit
Input Voltage	1.45	-	2	V
Temperature Range	-20	27	85	$^\circ C$
Output Voltage	1.192	1.2	1.205	V
Dropout Voltage	162	-	270	mV
LNR	0.025	-	0.059	%
LDR	0.0025	-	2.29	%/mA
TC	14	-	94	ppm/ $^\circ C$
Current Throughput	0.001	0.1	0.3	mA
PSRR@10MHz	-77.5	-43	-28.7	dB
Total Power	-	6.3	45	μW

V. DISCUSSION

The comparison of the proposed LDO to other works is presented in Table II. As can be observed, high PSR features are usually obtained by high value of the output capacitor, except for works [16], [17]. In [16], the value of output capacitor is smaller than in the other works thanks to a supply-ripple cancellation technique employed. However, the static current consumption was increased. On the other hand, in our research, where an NMOS transistor was used to cascode the PMOS device, the output capacitor value as well as static current consumption are smaller. If the slew-rate enhancement circuit is employed, the power consumption will be increased. Therefore, a compromise between the output capacitor size and power consumption needs to be taken in order to meet the low-power operation conditions and reach a

TABLE II
COMPARISON OF PROPOSED LDO TO OTHER WORKS

Reference	[13]	[14]	[15]	[16]	[17]	This work
Technology [nm]	130	350	65	65	180	65
Power transistor	N.A.	N.A.	PMOS	PMOS	N.A.	PMOS ⁽⁵⁾
V _{OUT} [V]	N.A.	N.A.	1.0	1.0	0.9 - 1.7	1.2
V _{DO} [mV]	150.0	300.0	150.0	200.0	200.0	205.4
I _Q [μ A]	50	40.6 - 76.8	150	8 ⁽²⁾ , 297.5 ⁽³⁾	1120 ⁽⁴⁾	4.19 μ ⁽⁶⁾ , 30 μ ⁽⁷⁾
I _{LOAD} [A]	25m	25m	25m	25m	20m	100 μ
LR [mV/mA]	N.A.	N.A.	0.040	0.042	0.5	0.038
C _L [F]	4 μ	5 μ	4.7 μ	240p	500p	150p
PSR [dB]						
@1 MHz	67	47	> 61	52	65	30.7
@10 MHz	56	66	47	36	31	43
@worst case	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	25.5@1 μ A 23@100 μ A 17@300 μ A
FOM ⁽¹⁾ [$\times 10^6$]	26.3	33.2	7.9	32862	7096	376

⁽¹⁾ $FOM = |PSR(10\text{ MHz})|I_Q/V_{DO}C_L$. ⁽²⁾No load. ⁽³⁾Full load. ⁽⁴⁾Calculated from reported current efficiency. ⁽⁵⁾With NMOS cascode. ⁽⁶⁾No slew-rate enhancement. ⁽⁷⁾With slew-rate enhancement.

good PSR performance of the on-chip LDO. For relevant and better comparison, we used Figure of Merit (FoM) introduced in [4] that proves excellent performance of the presented LDO topology. We should underline that in most cases, the good PSR performance was obtained by a large output capacitor and therefore, the proposed topology represents the best choice for on-chip implementation of LDO.

VI. CONCLUSION

The LDO topology based on PMOS pass device cascoded with the NMOS transistor, designed in 65 nm CMOS technology, was presented. As demonstrated, the designed LDO exhibits very good PSR performance even at high frequencies above 10 MHz. Obtained results shows that the proposed topology reaches small power consumption and PSR of -40 dB at frequencies above 10 MHz with a relatively small value of the output capacitor. Presented LDO represents good choice for ultra-low power SoC, where the PSR performance is very important.

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REFERENCES

- [1] V. Gupta and G. A. Rincon-Mora, "A low dropout, CMOS regulator with high PSR over wideband frequencies," in *2005 IEEE International Symposium on Circuits and Systems*, 2005, pp. 4245–4248 Vol. 5.
- [2] J. Zarate-Roldan, M. Wang, J. Torres, and E. Snchez-Sinencio, "A Capacitor-Less LDO With High-Frequency PSR Suitable for a Wide Range of On-Chip Capacitive Loads," *IEEE Transactions on Very Large Scale Integration (VLSI) Systems*, vol. 24, no. 9, pp. 2970–2982, 2016.
- [3] B. Yang, B. Drost, S. Rao, and P. K. Hanumolu, "A high-PSR LDO using a feedforward supply-noise cancellation technique," in *2011 IEEE Custom Integrated Circuits Conference (CICC)*, 2011, pp. 1–4.
- [4] K. Joshi, S. Manandhar, and B. Bakaloglu, "A 5.6uA Wide Bandwidth, High Power Supply Rejection Linear Low-Dropout Regulator With 68 dB of PSR Up To 2 MHz," *IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 55, no. 8, pp. 2151–2160, 2020.
- [5] I. Sularea, C. Rducun, and M. Neag, "A Capacitor-less LDO with High PSR over a wide frequency range," in *2021 International Semiconductor Conference (CAS)*, 2021, pp. 213–216.
- [6] J. Ingino and V. von Kaenel, "A 4-GHz clock system for a high-performance system-on-a-chip design," *IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 36, no. 11, pp. 1693–1698, 2001.
- [7] C.-H. Lee, K. McClellan, and J. Choma, "A supply-noise-insensitive CMOS PLL with a voltage regulator using DC-DC capacitive converter," *IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 36, no. 10, pp. 1453–1463, 2001.
- [8] X. Han, L. Wu, Y. Gao, and W.-H. Ki, "An Adaptively Biased Output-Capacitor-Free Low-Dropout Regulator With Supply Ripple Subtraction and Pole-Tracking-Compensation," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 36, no. 11, pp. 12795–12804, 2021.
- [9] T. Y. Man, P. K. T. Mok, and M. Chan, "A High Slew-Rate PushPull Output Amplifier for Low-Quiescent Current Low-Dropout Regulators With Transient-Response Improvement," *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems II: Express Briefs*, vol. 54, no. 9, pp. 755–759, 2007.
- [10] P. M. Furth, S. Krishnapurapu, S. H. Pakala, and M. A. Haque, "A 5.3uA quiescent current fully-integrated low-dropout (LDO) regulator with Transient Recovery Time Enhancement," in *2013 IEEE 56th International Midwest Symposium on Circuits and Systems (MWSCAS)*, 2013, pp. 9–12.
- [11] H. Valapala and P. M. Furth, "Analysis and design of fully integrated very low quiescent current LDOs," in *2012 IEEE 55th International Midwest Symposium on Circuits and Systems (MWSCAS)*, 2012, pp. 230–233.
- [12] D. Arbet, M. Poton, M. Kov, L. Nagy, and V. Stopjakov, "Fully on-chip low-drop regulator for low-power applications," in *2021 44th International Convention on Information, Communication and Electronic Technology (MIPRO)*, 2021, pp. 101–106.

- [13] M. El-Nozahi, A. Amer, J. Torres, K. Entesari, and E. Sanchez-Sinencio, "High psr low drop-out regulator with feed-forward ripple cancellation technique," *IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 45, no. 3, pp. 565–577, 2010.
- [14] S. Yeung, J. Guo, and K. Leung, "25 ma ldo with -63 db psrr at 30 mhz for wimax," *Electronics Letters*, vol. 46, pp. 1080 – 1081, 08 2010.
- [15] Y.-S. Yuk, S. Jung, C. Kim, H.-D. Gwon, S. Choi, and G.-H. Cho, "Psr enhancement through super gain boosting and differential feed-forward noise cancellation in a 65-nm cmos ldo regulator," *IEEE Transactions on Very Large Scale Integration (VLSI) Systems*, vol. 22, no. 10, pp. 2181–2191, 2014.
- [16] Y. Lim, J. Lee, S. Park, Y. Jo, and J. Choi, "An external capacitorless low-dropout regulator with high psr at all frequencies from 10 khz to 1 ghz using an adaptive supply-ripple cancellation technique," *IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 53, no. 9, pp. 2675–2685, 2018.
- [17] C.-Y. Tseng, L.-W. Wang, and P.-C. Huang, "An integrated linear regulator with fast output voltage transition for dual-supply srams in dvfs systems," *IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 45, no. 11, pp. 2239–2249, 2010.